

EFFECTIVENESS OF PHYSICAL THERAPY IN CORNELIA DE LANGE SYNDROME

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Abstract. Cornelia de Lange Syndrome (CdLS) is a rare genetic disorder caused by mutations in various genes. It is mainly characterized by severe mental retardation, physical growth retardation, and abnormalities in the development of upper and lower limbs. According to various studies, CdLS is a multisystem disorder that affects physical, cognitive, and behavioral characteristics. For instance, in the USA about 3,800 cases have been registered, while EUROCAT data from 1980–2002 reported 106 cases among 8,558,346 births in Europe. The exact prevalence remains uncertain, though it is estimated to occur in approximately 1 in 10,000 live births, with some estimates suggesting 1 in 30,000. In Georgia, a total of 4 cases have been registered — 2 in Batumi and 2 in Tbilisi.

This syndrome is still under investigation worldwide due to the small number of identified patients. As noted, currently there are 4 known cases in Georgia. One of these patients began treatment at 7 months of age when developmental delays became apparent. This article is primarily a review, with partial research elements, aiming to assist physical therapists and parents in focusing on early intervention to improve gross motor function, which in turn enhances the patient’s overall condition.

ფიზიკური თერაპიის ეფექტურობა კორნელია დე ლანგეს სინდრომის დროს

ელისო მურვანიძე

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აბსტრაქტი. კორნელია დე ლანგეს სინდრომი (CdLS) იშვიათი გენეტიკური დაავადებაა, რომელიც გამოწვეულია სხვადასხვა გენებში მუტაციებით. იგი ძირითადად ხასიათდება მძიმე გონებრივი ჩამორჩენილობით, ფიზიკური ზრდის ჩამორჩენილობით და ზედა და ქვედა კიდურების განვითარების ანომალიებით. სხვადასხვა კვლევის თანახმად, CdLS არის მულტისისტემური დაავადება, რომელიც გავლენას ახდენს ფიზიკურ, კოგნიტურ და ქცევით მახასიათებლებზე. მაგალითად, აშშ-ში დაახლოებით 3800 შემთხვევაა რეგისტრირებული, ხოლო EUROCAT-ის 1980-2002 წლების მონაცემებით, ევროპაში 8558346 დაბადებიდან 106 შემთხვევა დაფიქსირდა. ზუსტი გავრცელება გაურკვეველი რჩება, თუმცა, სავარაუდოდ, ის დაახლოებით 10000 ცოცხლად დაბადებიდან 1-ში გვხვდება, ზოგიერთი შეფასებით კი 30000-დან 1-ში. საქართველოში სულ 4 შემთხვევაა რეგისტრირებული - 2 ბაღში და 2 თბილისში. ეს სინდრომი ჯერ კიდევ კვლევის პროცესშია მსოფლიო მასშტაბით იდენტიფიცირებული პაციენტების მცირე რაოდენობის გამო. როგორც აღინიშნა, ამჟამად საქართველოში 4 ცნობილი შემთხვევაა. ამ პაციენტებიდან ერთ-ერთმა მკურნალობა 7 თვის ასაკში დაიწყო, როდესაც განვითარების შეფერხება აშკარა გახდა. ეს სტატია,

ძირითადად, წარმოადგენს მიმოხილვას, ნაწილობრივი კვლევითი ელემენტებით, რომლის მიზანია დაეხმაროს ფიზიოთერაპევტებსა და მშობლებს ადრეულ ჩარევაზე ფოკუსირებაში უხეში მოტორული ფუნქციის გასაუმჯობესებლად, რაც, თავის მხრივ, აუმჯობესებს პაციენტის საერთო მდგომარეობას.

Introduction

The first patient with Cornelia de Lange Syndrome was officially described in 1916 by the German physician Winfried Robert Clemens Brachmann (1888–1969). Working in a pediatric clinic, Brachmann documented in detail the condition of a 19-day-old infant. [1,3,6]

In approximately 3 out of 10 cases, the cause of CdLS remains unknown. In the remaining cases, its development is attributed to mutations in five specific genes: **NIPBL**, **SMC1A**, **HDAC8**, **RAD21**, and **SMC3**. Depending on which gene is mutated, the disorder may be inherited in an autosomal dominant manner (when a single defective gene from one parent is sufficient to cause the pathology) or be X-linked. However, in most cases, CdLS results from a **de novo mutation**, meaning it arises spontaneously during early embryogenesis rather than being inherited. [2,4,10]

The most common genetic mutation associated with CdLS is damage to the **NIPBL gene**. The NIPBL (Nipped-B-like) gene is responsible for proper loading and activation of the cohesin complex. It is located on chromosome 5p13. About 60–70% of CdLS cases are linked to mutations in this gene. Other associated genes include:

- **SMC1A** – Located on the X chromosome; mutations often result in milder clinical manifestations, though effects are more pronounced in males (who have only one X chromosome).
- **SMC3** – Associated with a less severe phenotype; CdLS due to this gene is relatively rare.
- **RAD21** – Causes phenotypic variability and can present with symptoms of differing severity.
- **HDAC8** – Associated with milder forms and influences chromatin modification.

In most cases, these mutations arise **de novo**, meaning they occur spontaneously rather than being inherited. [3,4,8]

This paper specifically discusses the **classical CdLS phenotype** associated with **NIPBL mutations**.

Objectives:

To study the characteristic features of Cornelia de Lange Syndrome, review the research conducted by various scholars, and identify patients with this syndrome in Georgia.

Materials and Methods:

The symptoms of Cornelia de Lange Syndrome vary in degree and severity but generally include physical, neuropsychological, and developmental abnormalities.

Physical

signs:

CdLS is characterized by distinctive phenotypic features that may be apparent at birth, including:

- **Facial dysmorphism** (arched and confluent eyebrows, microcephaly or brachycephaly, limb anomalies, etc.)
- **Motor development:** Delayed walking, hypotonia, and coordination problems are common; some cases present with ataxia.
- **Social development:** Limited socialization skills requiring targeted stimulation. Without early intervention, social isolation and communication deficits are frequent.
- **Adaptive skills:** Independence in daily functioning is often limited; self-care skills usually lag behind chronological age.

The manifestations are highly variable — some patients exhibit only a few of these signs, while others show all. [9,10,11,17]

Few studies describe adult patients with CdLS. Research conducted on two adult groups (total of 122 patients, aged 15–50 years; mean ages 17 and 24) indicated signs of premature aging. The most common medical problems included:

- Gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD): 71–82%
- Overweight/obesity: 16–31%
- Limb length discrepancy: 26–46%
- Epilepsy: 26%
- Hearing impairment: 42–65%
- Vision problems: 38–50%
- Behavioral disorders: 50%

Results:

Children with CdLS generally require physical therapy; however, evidence supporting its effectiveness in this population is limited. Researchers reviewed six databases, including MEDLINE/PubMed, SCOPUS, PEDro, CINAHL, and EBSCO.

Between July 2006 and February 2022, only English-language studies investigating the role of physical therapy in CdLS patients were included. A total of 12 articles were identified, with 6 considered high-quality for review.

The analysis was structured into three phases focusing on key challenges such as growth and developmental delay, hearing loss, and muscle weakness. In particular, therapy emphasized strengthening of the trunk, back, and lower limb muscles — especially the paraspinal muscles — which are often problematic in individuals with CdLS.

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Table 1. Physical Therapy Treatment Strategy by Phases in CdLS

Phase	Pathological Development in CdLS Patient	Goals	Treatment
1 Phase	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulty attracting the child's attention • Delayed developmental milestones • Growth and developmental problems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encourage attention and engagement • Guide the child toward normal developmental activities • Improve head control 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Place moving or sound-producing objects in various directions to stimulate attention • Perform passive exercises for the trunk and limbs to increase mobility and endurance for improved functional performance • Correct abnormal postures • Improve head control and facilitate free head movement in a vertical position
2 Phase	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unable to sit • Unable to stand • Unable to roll over • Unable to walk 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teach sitting with or without support • Train supported standing • Practice assisted rolling 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exercises for rolling, sitting, crawling, and supported standing • Improve balance and coordination • Use of balance board • Standing and walking with a walker
3 Phase	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Muscle weakness • Weakness in upper and lower limbs • Weakness of abdominal extensor muscles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continue goals from previous phases • Encourage participation in special education • Engage in ball play • Activate and strengthen upper and lower limb extensor muscles • Strengthen abdominal extensor muscles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintain passive exercises for upper and lower limbs • Strengthen upper and lower limb extensor muscles • Balance training • Develop physical endurance and stamina

The aim of this study was to explore and summarize the use of physical therapy within the Cornelia de Lange Syndrome (CdLS) population. CdLS is a rare genetic disorder that typically arises due to developmental mutations, affecting growth and development. It is often associated with low birth weight, swallowing difficulties, gastroesophageal reflux, hearing impairment, and

distinctive facial features [9]. Treatment protocols generally include **physical therapy**, **occupational therapy**, and **speech therapy**.

Conclusion

Findings indicate that patients with chronic impairment may benefit from physical therapy in diverse ways, highlighting its crucial role in management and rehabilitation. Physical therapy contributes to the improvement of motor function and mobility. It represents an effective strategy in the rehabilitation of individuals with CdLS by helping to normalize muscle tone, relieve pain, promote active movement, and enhance functional abilities in daily living activities.

The purpose of this review is to ensure that children with CdLS receive the best possible physiotherapeutic care and experience.

Case Description (Georgia)

In Georgia, a total of **four children** with CdLS have been registered:

- Two children (male, aged 4 and 5) live in **Tbilisi**.
- Two children (female, aged 8; male, aged 11) live in **Batumi**.

This article describes the case of a **4-year-old male** diagnosed with Cornelia de Lange Syndrome. The child presents with **severe mental impairment** but **moderate physical involvement**. He began physical therapy at the age of **7 months** due to noticeable developmental delays.

Functional abilities:

- Sits independently.
- Can stand with support and maintain standing without assistance when holding onto an object.
- Performs turns and can walk short distances with one-hand assistance.
- Walks independently for **30–50 steps**.
- Can transfer a toy from one hand to the other and bring it to his mouth.

Developmental milestones:

- Independent sitting began at **14 months**.
- Independent standing at **38 months**.
- Independent walking at **44 months**.

Therapeutic Interventions:

The child has been receiving **regular physical therapy** since 7 months of age — **5 days per week**. In addition:

- **Occupational therapy** twice weekly since age 2.
- **Speech therapy** twice weekly since age 3.

- **Special education** interventions since 2 years and 6 months of age.

Physical therapy activities include:

- Passive mobilization of upper and lower limbs.
- Assisted pelvic lifts.
- Assisted sit-to-stand exercises.
- Supported standing.
- Development of protective reactions (safe falling responses).
- Gait training for independent walking.
- Balance exercises using a balance board.

Summary and Conclusion

Since CdLS is a rare genetic disorder, conducting large-scale studies is difficult. However, based on previously reviewed literature and the Georgian patient observation, it can be concluded that **early physical therapy intervention is crucial** for improving physical condition and overall development.

In conclusion: Early physical therapy in Cornelia de Lange Syndrome is effective in improving **upper and lower limb mobility**, enhancing overall **motor function**, and facilitating **better adaptation** in social environments through improved physical abilities.

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